

A Sparsity based approach to Velocity SAR Imaging

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Abstract— We recently successfully developed an airborne MSAR (Multichannel Synthetic Aperture Radar) test bed system that consists of 32 along-track phase centers through the use of two transmit horns and 16 receive antennas [1-4]. We have subsequently deployed this system, both in September 2014 and more recently in October 2015, to perform extensive and systematic data collections on a variety of land-based and maritime targets under different environmental conditions. The resulting data poses important signal processing challenges pertaining to optimum ways of combining the signals obtained from various channels so that the underlying information of interest can be effectively extracted in the presence of noise and clutter. In this paper we focus on the imaging problem and propose a novel method of simultaneously exploiting the multichannel structure of the data acquisition and the underlying sparse structure of the scene being imaged. After giving a brief overview of our airborne NRL MSAR system and the basics of velocity processing, we proceed to describe our novel algorithm and demonstrate our initial experimental results. The novelty of this paper is two-fold: to the best of our knowledge, this is first time that velocity processing has been used in conjunction with sparsity based processing; and that the resulting approach is applied to real data captured by our airborne NRL MSAR system.

Keywords—Imaging; Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR); Multichannel SAR (MSAR); Sparsity; Velocity Processing; Wavelets

I. NRL MSAR SYSTEM

The NRL MSAR is an airborne system based on the NRL Focused Phased Array Imaging Radar (FOPAIR), a ground-based MSAR test bed [3, 5]. The MSAR system operates at X-band with a center frequency of 9.875 GHz and uses linear FM chirped waveforms with a bandwidth of 220 MHz to achieve a range resolution of approximately 0.7 m. The peak radiated power is approximately 1.4 kW, while the aggregate pulse repetition frequency (PRF) of 25 kHz and pulse length of 6 μ s produce an average power of 210 W. The system flies on a Saab 340 aircraft using a belly-mounted radome with a nominal incidence angle of 70°. Typical altitude and airspeeds are 914 m (3000 ft.) and 70 m/s, respectively.

Fig. 1 shows a schematic of our airborne system for data collection of land and maritime targets; and Fig. 2 shows a close-up of the radome and our MSAR system. The airborne MSAR system consists of two modularly constructed 16 channel sections from FOPAIR. Though we had a maximum of 16 receive elements in our MSAR system, due to our on-board data storage constraints we received on every other element which was found to be the maximum that we could process while still providing sufficient velocity resolution. To improve the system still further we used two independent transmitters, one at either end of the array to effectively double the number

of phase centers (and halve the minimum detectable velocity). This system provides up to 32 velocity bins from 1 to 20 m/s with a resolution of 0.7 m/s.

All elements are vertically polarized. During odd-numbered pulse repetition intervals (PRIs), the aft-mounted horn transmits an ‘up’ chirp, while during even PRIs, the fore-mounted horn radiates a ‘down’ chirp. During each pair of up-down PRIs, four of the 16 consecutive and alternative receive elements are connected to a four-channel receiver and sampled by a high speed data recorder. After each pair of PRIs, a bank of microwave switches is reconfigured to connect the next group of four (consecutive and alternative) receive elements to the receiver and data recorder. After a total of 4 up-chirp/down-chirp PRI pairs (320 μ s), this scan sequence is repeated. In this manner, 32 phase centers corresponding to each combination of transmit and receive antennas are generated and sampled at a per phase-center PRF of 3.125 kHz. This PRF is sufficient to allow production of 32 SAR images, one corresponding to each phase center, that are free from azimuthal (cross-range) ambiguities.

Since the location of a given phase center is halfway between the corresponding transmit and receive antennas, the along track spacing between these phase centers is 5.24 cm, half the physical spacing between the receive elements. Note that given the spacing between the two transmit horns, four of the phase centers corresponding to the aft-mounted transmit horn are collocated with four produced by the fore-mounted horn. Thus the total number of independent phase centers is 28 with total length of 141.5 cm.

Finally in the hardware configuration of our system that was deployed in September 2014, there was a mismatch in the spectral shapes between the up-chirp and down-chirp channels resulting in channel incoherence that made the use of more than 16 of the 32 channels (i.e. either from up-chirp or from down-chirp) difficult. This hardware problem was resolved in our subsequent October 2015 deployment (resulting in 32 effective channels).

We have deployed the NRL MSAR system, in September 2014 and more recently in October 2015, to perform extensive and systematic data collections on a variety of land-based and maritime targets under different environmental conditions. The resulting datasets pose important signal processing challenges pertaining to optimum ways of combining the signals obtained from various channels so that the underlying information of interest can be effectively extracted in the presence of noise and clutter.

In the next section we describe how the multichannel structure offered by our NRL MSAR system can be harnessed via a procedure called *velocity SAR (VSAR) processing*.

II. EXPLOITING MULTICHANNEL STRUCTURE

The presence of multiple phase centers facilitates the measurement of signal phase progression across the channels which in turn allows for the calculation of Doppler spread of scatterer velocities associated with each pixel in the image. In the late 1990s, the theoretical work of Friedlander and Porat [6] showed how this information can be utilized by VSAR processing to form a coherent fusion of multiple SAR images (one for each phase center)—called the VSAR image—that, as suggested in their initial studies [6], tends to focus scatterers much better than individual SAR images. The scope and effectiveness of VSAR processing has subsequently been characterized in more detail by recent experimental works [1-5].

In the VSAR scheme, each channel is treated independently by coherently summing pulses across the whole collection, as one would with a single channel SAR. This approach creates multiple SAR images, one per phase center. The next step is to perform a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) for each pixel along the time stack. The result is a velocity profile (i.e. distribution of scatterer velocities) for each pixel location. In order to correct for motion, we then shift each velocity component back to the origin and summed the resulting images to form the VSAR image.

Apart from providing a method for obtaining the radial velocity spectrum automatically from first principles (at every pixel in the image), another advantage to the VSAR method is that it retains the full image resolution available for the entire collection duration. The velocity resolution in this VSAR approach is inversely proportional to the number of channels M . As shown by the analysis in [6], the structure point spread function (psf) associated with each azimuthal location in the image, assuming a constant range, has a product structure between the velocity window of size M and the azimuthal window of size N (where N is the number of pulses transmitted). It is this product structure that jointly shapes the resulting psf such that scatterers at azimuthal location x_0 and velocity v_0 are localized to the corresponding (location, velocity) tuple in the azimuth-velocity plane. A difficulty with VSAR velocity estimation is that it produces only radial motion estimates (at each pixel) and thus it can be difficult to get a full understanding of the complete motion if it is complicated. This difficulty can be circumvented by using sub-aperture approaches VSAR processing as we have explored in [3]. In this paper, however, we only focus on VSAR processing. We further point out that due to channel and antenna imperfections, additional processing may be needed to further enhance phase coherency across channels [1-2]. In the experiments in Section V, however, channel balancing was not applied as it did not significantly improve the imaging results for the particular boat that we image in this paper.

In the VSAR scheme described above it is important to distinguish between the SAR imaging step (performed independently by each phase center) from the *velocity processing* step which consists of sorting out the velocities associated with each spatial location (via the FFT operator), shifting them so that they align with the correct velocity bin, and finally incoherently summing them.

We further observe the velocity processing is essentially independent of the particular method that is used to form the individual images from each phase center. Indeed different applications may call for alternative methods of image formation. For example in [2] we showed when imaging rigid bodies in maritime conditions, superior overall image quality can be obtained by combining velocity processing with ISAR imaging (which we call VISAR imaging).

In this paper we explore a novel method for image formation wherein a sparsity-based approach to SAR imaging is combined with the velocity processing procedure.

III. EXPLOITING SPARSITY STRUCTURE IN SAR IMAGING

Independent of the various radar imaging modalities, it has been recognized over the past 2 decades that a very powerful statistical characteristic of signals derived from empirical sources—especially those pertaining to imagery—is that they admit a sparse structure with respect to various time/space-frequency like bases such as wavelets [7]. In other words, the inherent complexity of the underlying empirical source is much simpler 'than meets the eye'; and that this structure is revealed when analyzing the signals in the appropriate bases.

Moreover algorithmic advancements in signal processing, under the rubric of compressive sensing, have further revealed how this sparsity structure can be systematically exploited (via the solution of convex optimization programs) to infer the underlying structural information of interest given the corresponding empirical measurements [8-10]. This formulation encompasses a very broad class of statistical estimation problems, including SAR imaging [11-12], which we are concerned with in this paper. Though there can be many possible implementations of sparsity based [11]—or more generally, Bayesian [9-10]—SAR Imaging, in this paper we employ the approach due to Samadi et. al. [12].

Let $s(x, y)$ denote the spatial reflectivity of the target scene to be imaged (where (x, y) denotes the spatial coordinates associated with the imaging plane), and $g(f, \theta)$ denote the received signal at the sensor (where f denotes the frequency of the waveform, and θ denotes the sensing angle). Then we have that:

$$g(f_k, \theta_l) = \sum_{m=1}^M s(x_m, y_m) e^{-j\frac{4\pi f_k}{c}(x_m \cos \theta_l + y_m \sin \theta_l)} + n(f_k, \theta_l) \quad (1)$$

where, n is the additive noise component of the received signal. The observation model (1) can be cast into a more convenient vector form:

$$g = \Psi s + n \quad (2)$$

where, vectors r , s , and n are vectorized versions of $g(f_k, \theta_l)$, $s(x_m, y_m)$, and $n(f_k, \theta_l)$ respectively. Ψ is the sensing matrix that can be derived directly from Equation (1).

We model the source vector s as follows: $s = \Phi c$, where Φ is a matrix whose columns consist of different wavelet atoms (more generally any time/space-frequency like bases), and c is a vector of unknown coefficients. A complication that arises in SAR imaging, that is not present in optical imaging, is that the coefficients c are complex due to the fact the scatterers in the

scene induce a phase structure on the electromagnetic response. In order to accommodate this within convex optimization algorithms, the equation (2) can be recast as follows [12].

First let $c = D\alpha$, where α is a vector of real coefficients and D is a diagonal matrix consisting of phase terms: $D = \text{diag}\{e^{j\phi_k}\}$. Further in order to render the receive vector as range profiles, we pre-multiply the matrix Ψ with matrix F^{-1} which is a block diagonal matrix where each block performs the IDFT (Inverse Discrete Fourier Transform) on the backscatter response corresponding to each sensing angle. Thus we obtain the following model for our SAR imaging:

$$r = F^{-1}g = F^{-1}\Psi D\alpha + n \quad (3)$$

$$= F^{-1}\Psi D\Phi\alpha + n \quad (4)$$

$$\equiv HD\Phi\alpha + n \quad (5)$$

where: $H = F^{-1}\Psi$, (4) is valid because D is a diagonal matrix, and by a slight abuse of notation the same symbol n is used for noise in equations (3-5).

Given the radar measurements r , the only unknowns in equation (5) are the entries of vector α and the (diagonal) entries of matrix D . First we initialize the vector α from the backprojection image [13] formed from the measurement vector r . Given this we can fix the estimate of D , and solve for the resulting equation in terms of α via a convex optimization program:

$$\alpha^{opt} = \text{argmin}_{\alpha} J_1(\alpha) \quad (6)$$

where: $J_1(\alpha) = \|r - HD\Phi\alpha\|_2^2 + \lambda_1 \|\alpha\|_p^p$, and $\|\cdot\|_p$ denotes the l_p norm for $p \geq 0$. It is well known in signal processing and statistics literature that $p \leq 1$ enforces sparsity in the representation. In all our experiments below we used $p = 0.7$ in order to promote sparsity in the solutions.

Given the estimate of α from (6) above, we then solve for the optimum phase estimates by solving the following convex optimization problem:

$$\beta^{opt} = \text{argmin}_{\beta} J_2(\beta) \quad (7)$$

where: $J_2(\beta) = \|r - HB\beta\|_2^2 + \lambda_2 \|\beta\|_2^2 - 2\lambda_2 \|\beta\|_1$
 $B \equiv \text{diag}((\Phi\alpha)_i)$

It can be easily shown that the optimization problem (7) is equivalent to the following problem:

$$\beta^{opt} = \text{argmin}_{\beta} \|r - HD\Phi\beta\|_2^2 \quad (8)$$

subject to $|\beta_i| = 1$ for all i

While (8) is clearly the desired phase optimization problem, the advantage of (7) is that it is a convex re-formulation of (8) which is hence guaranteed to converge to a global minimum (of the sub-problem being solved).

We computationally implemented (6) using the approach outlined in [12] whereby we first approximate $\|\alpha\|_p^p$ by $\sum_i (|\alpha_i|^2 + \epsilon)^{p/2}$. We chose $\epsilon = 10^{-5}$ in our experiments in Section IV. Given this, we perform the following Quasi-Newton iterations to solve for α [12]:

$$\alpha^{(n+1)} = \alpha^{(n)} - \gamma_1 [G(\alpha^{(n)})]^{-1} \nabla_{\alpha} J(\alpha^{(n)}) \quad (10)$$

where:

$$G(\alpha) = 2(HD\Phi)^H(HD\Phi) + \lambda p \Lambda(\alpha)$$

$$\Lambda(\alpha) = \text{diag}\{1/(|\alpha_i|^2 + \epsilon)^{1-\epsilon/2}\}$$

$$\nabla_{\alpha} J(\alpha) = G(\alpha)\alpha - 2(HD\Phi)^H y$$

In order to circumvent the explicit calculation of the matrix inverse of $G(\alpha^{(n)})$ in (10), we rearrange (10) as follows [12]:

$$G(\alpha^{(n)})\alpha^{(n+1)} = (1 - \gamma_1)G(\alpha^{(n)})\alpha^{(n)} + 2\gamma_1(HD\Phi)^H y \quad (11)$$

Equation (11) can be solved efficiently via CG (Conjugate Gradient) techniques [14].

Similarly when solving for the optimum phase component via equation (7), similar Quasi-Newton iterations are performed by solving for $\beta^{(n+1)}$ via a CG approach [12]:

$$G(\beta^{(n)})\beta^{(n+1)} = (1 - \gamma_2)\tilde{G}\beta^{(n)} + 2\gamma_2(HB)^H y + 2\gamma_2\lambda_2\varphi(\beta^{(n)}) \quad (13)$$

where:

$$\tilde{G} = 2(HB)^H HB + 2\lambda_2 I$$

$$(\varphi(\beta^{(n)}))_i = e^{j(\varphi(\beta^{(n)}))_i} \quad \text{for all } i$$

$$I \equiv \text{Identity Matrix}$$

The Quasi-Newton iterations of $\alpha^{(n)}$ and $\beta^{(n)}$ proceed until $\|\alpha^{(n+1)} - \alpha^{(n)}\|_2^2 / \|\alpha^{(n)}\|_2^2 \leq \delta_1$ and $\|\beta^{(n+1)} - \beta^{(n)}\|_2^2 / \|\beta^{(n)}\|_2^2 \leq \delta_2$ respectively.

IV. SPARSITY BASED VSAR IMAGING

The velocity and sparsity based processing described in the preceding two sections exploit complimentary aspects of MSAR imaging. While Sparsity based SAR imaging attempts to exploit a priori knowledge of the statistical structure of the scene in order to form improved estimates of the SAR image, velocity processing corrects the motion error associated with each pixel by exploiting the phase structure across the different phase centers.

Based on the above exposition, our Sparsity based SAR imaging algorithm can now be succinctly summarized as follows:

- 1) Perform basic radar pre-processing steps such as pulse compression [15] to obtain the range profile corresponding to each phase center
- 2) For each frame, perform Sparsity based imaging using the techniques described above. In particular, iterate between:
 - a) Optimization of wavelet coefficients $\alpha^{(n)}$
 - b) Optimization of phase $\beta^{(n)}$

Until $\|f^{(n+1)} - f^{(n)}\|_2^2 / \|f^{(n)}\|_2^2 \leq \delta$
where: $f^{(n)} = \Phi(\text{diag}\{\beta^{(n)}\} * \alpha^{(n)})$
- 3) Combine the SAR image frames obtained above by incorporating a velocity filtering procedure similar to that employed in VSAR [6]:
 - a) The incoherent summation of the different shifted velocity frames furnishes the Sparsity based VSAR image.
 - b) Alternatively the maximum at each pixel (for the shifted velocity frames) can be calculated to obtain

the dominant velocity map corresponding to the target being imaged

In our experiments we chose Φ to be a dictionary of Biorthogonal 1.1 wavelet [7] atoms for a 256x256 image. The sensing matrix Ψ is constructed in a straightforward manner from equation (1). The SAR images, corresponding to each channel of the MSAR system, are formed by projecting the respective phase-history data onto a 256x256 grid via the backprojection algorithm [16]. As explained in Section II, the VSAR image is formed by a coherent fusion of these SAR images obtained across all the channels. These SAR images, as explained in Section III, also form the initialization to our Sparsity based VSAR imaging algorithm.

For the sparsity based optimization phase, the following parameter settings were used: $\lambda_1 = 4$, $\gamma_1 = 1$, $\delta_1 = 0.01$, $\lambda_2 = 2$, $\gamma_2 = 1$, $\delta_2 = 0.01$, and $\delta = 0.1$. Furthermore, as described in Section III, $p = 0.7$ and $\epsilon = 10^{-5}$ were used for the sparsifying l_p norm.

In the next section we demonstrate the performance of our Sparsity based Velocity SAR algorithm by imaging a boat sensed by our airborne NRL MSAR system.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND CONCLUDING REMARKS

Figure 3(a) shows an optical image of a boat that was captured by our NRL MSAR system in September 2014. When capturing this particular dataset our plane flew at an altitude of about 6000 ft. and performed a circular track of radius 2.5 km. During this time the boat was stationary. For this collection geometry, the boat was roughly at the center of the antenna beam (which encompassed a circle on the ground-plane with radius of approximately 500m) for the entire duration of the collection interval. There were no other significant interfering targets within this beamwidth during the data capture.

In Figure 3(b)-(c) we show the results of applying the VSAR and Sparsity-based VSAR algorithms on the phase history data (corresponding to the boat in Figure 3(a)) that comprises of 701 pulses and 31 range-bins. Figures 3(d)-(e) shows the corresponding zoomed versions to enable better viewing ability. While the above parameter settings of the Sparsity based VSAR algorithm marginally improves the sharpness of the overall image, it mainly emphasizes complementary features of the boat being imaged.

The potential advantage afforded by the Sparsity based VSAR algorithm is primarily in its ability to control the sparsity levels (and sharpness of focus) by adjusting the parameters λ_1 and p . The high computational complexity of the current implementation of Sparsity based VSAR limits it to small chip sizes; and also renders it difficult to perform quick search of optimum parameters for imaging.

Circumventing these challenges together with alternative means of phase optimization are open problems emerging from this work. The true validation of sparsity based imaging techniques in radar however is contingent, in our opinion, on its successful application to target recognition [17] problems.

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Figure 1: Schematic of the NRL Airborne MSAR System (successfully deployed in September 2014 and October 2015)

Figure 2: NRL MSAR in its Radome

Figure 3(a): Optical Image of Boat

Figure 3(b): VSAR Image of Boat:
Imaged on the 256x256 grid via
Backprojection algorithm [16]

Figure 3(c): Sparsity based VSAR Image of Boat
corresponding to Figure 3(b)

Figure 3(d): Cropped version of
VSAR Image of Boat in Figure 3(b)

Figure 3(e): Cropped version of Sparsity based VSAR
Image of Boat in Figure 3(c)